

Appendix B

Figure 1 represents the confusion matrices for the ensemble models using all the base models on Translated PROMISE_exp, and Figure 2 for the ensemble models using all the base models on ReSpa (the independent analysis on both cases).

Figure 1: Confusion matrix - Translated PROMISE_exp and all base models (a) Voting models, (b) Stacking BNB, (c) Stacking LR, (d) Stacking SVM, (e) Stacking MLP

Figure 2: Confusion matrix - ReSpa and all base models (a) Voting models, (b) Stacking BNB, (c) Stacking LR, (d) Stacking SVM, (e) Stacking MLP